

Hypervalent iodine oxidation of flavonols and 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones in different alcohols

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Abstract : Flavonols and 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones react with diacetoxyiodobenzene (DAIB) in different alcohols to yield addition compound. Alcohols used as solvent in the oxidation process add to the C-2 carbon of both the flavonols and 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones.

Keywords : Hypervalent iodine oxidation, flavonol, 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones, diacetoxyiodobenzene, 3,3-dihydroxy-2-alkoxyflavanone.

Introduction

Hypervalent iodine oxidation of flavonols (**1**) in methanol was reported to yield 2,3-dimethoxy-3-hydroxy flavanones (**2**) in good to excellent yield^{1,2}. Various oxidizing agents like DDQ^{3,10}, Cu-salts⁴, Tl^{III} acetate⁵, Tl^{III} nitrate⁵ and Pb^{IV} acetate⁶, peracids in methanol are also known to effect this conversion. A thorough literature survey revealed that synthesis of ethoxy or any other alkoxy analogue of **2** is not known so far. Similar is the situation with the styryl analogue of **3**. However, easy

availability of flavonols and 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones encouraged the authors to undertake synthesis of different alkoxy analogues of **2** and **3**.

The authors first carried out the oxidation reactions of flavonol using hypervalent iodine reagent, diacetoxyiodobenzene (DAIB) in monohydric alcohols methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and t-butanol at room temperature. Treatment of **1** in methanol using DAIB yielded compound **2** with good yield (78%). From the reactions of **1** in ethanol and isopropanol one product (**4**) could be isolated but reaction in t-butanol failed to furnish any pure product. Reaction of **1** with PhI(OAc)₂ in ethylene glycol afforded **5** at room temperature.

The compound 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromone (**6**), prepared from *o*-hydroxy- ω -cinnamyledene acetophenone (**7**), then separately treated with DAIB/MeOH and DAIB/EtOH

at room temperature to obtain product **3**. In neither of these two cases the desired product **3** could be obtained. Instead, compound **10** was obtained in good yield. However, treatment of **6** with *t*-butanol under similar reaction condition did not give any pure product.

Results and discussion

Flavonol was easily oxidized by diacetoxyiodobenzene, $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ reagent in ethanol, isopropanol and ethylene glycol to give addition product of the solvent used in each case. Solvent ethanol and isopropanol produced 3,3-dihydroxy-2-ethoxyflavanone and 3,3-dihydroxy-2-isopropoxyflavanone respectively by reacting with flavonol at room temperature. The desired 2,3-dialkoxy-3-hydroxyflavanones could not be obtained from reaction of flavonol (**1**) with DAIB in ethanol and isopropanol. Failure to the formation of 2,3-dialkoxy compounds from reaction of flavonol with $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ may be due to larger size of the alcohols used during the course of reaction. The authors became interested to see the outcome of the reaction using ethylene glycol as solvent because in this case one molecule of the solvent is expected to serve the purpose of two molecules of monohydric alcohol. However, the reaction of flavonol (**1**) with $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ in ethylene glycol afforded a colourless product (**5**) at room temperature as addition product of one molecule of ethylene glycol as per expectation of the authors. But, the reaction of 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromone (**6**) with DAIB in ethylene glycol under similar reaction condition failed to fur-

nish any pure product. It is to be mentioned here that the reaction of **1** and **6** in different alcohols at temperature up to 50° also gave same products.

[Similar mechanistic pathway can be followed for formation of compound **10** from **6**]

Probable Mechanism for formation of **4**.

It may be pointed out here that in none of the reports of the synthesis of **2** mentioned above, the configuration of the compounds was settled. But, Dey *et al.* reported⁸ that the compound like **8** may have the configuration as shown below.

From mechanistic point of view, it is observed that both **4** and **8** are formed following similar mechanism. So, it may be concluded that the compound **4** will have similar configuration as in the **8**. It has also been supported from the report⁹ of Mallik *et al.* They have reported that heterocyclic ring of this type of compound has a half-chair conformation with *trans* alkoxy substitution and this could be represented by the following diagram (**9**). It is to be noted that none of the compound of **4** gave quality crystal for carrying out X-ray crystallographic studies.

From the diagram of **9**, it is clear that some steric hindrance between Ar and R is present in the molecule. So, it might be the reason why **2** is formed when R=Me but similar compounds do not form when size of R > Me.

It may be pointed out here that two intramolecular H-bondings have been shown for 3,3-dihydroxy-2-methoxyflavanone in the report⁷ of Smith *et al.* following the Dreiding Model : (i) intramolecular H-bonding between one hydroxyl group at C-3 and the O-atom of the methoxy group at C-2, (ii) intramolecular H-bonding between another hydroxyl group at C-3 and the O-atom of the heterocyclic ring. However, from the X-ray crystallographic studies of *trans*-2,3-dimethoxy-3-(*p*-formylphenylamino)-4'-nitroflavanones⁹. Mallik *et al.* have shown that the intramolecular H-bonding occurs between the H-atom of β -NH(Ar) group and O-atom of $>C=O$ group in the half chair conformation. Thus, considering the report^{8,9} of Dey *et al.* and Mallik *et al.*, it is expected that β -OH group may take part in forming the intramolecular H-bonding as shown in the structure **9**.

Experimental

Procedure for the preparation of flavonol :

A solution of 2-hydroxychalcone (6 g, 0.0267 mole) in MeOH (25 ml) was added to a solution of NaOH (7.5 g, 0.187 mole) in water (25 ml). Then 30% H₂O₂ (20 ml) was added to the resulting solution during 10–15 min in 0 °C. The reaction mixture was set aside for 24 h and then acidified with dilute HCl. A light yellow solid separated out. The solid was filtered, washed with water (30 ml) and dried. The crude product was re-crystallized from methanol, m.p. 167–168 °C.

Procedure for the preparation of 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromone (**6**) :

To a solution of *o*-hydroxy- ω -cinnamylidene acetophenone (**7**) (1.06 g) in ethanol (15 ml), aq. NaOH (20 ml,

10 ml) was added. To this mixture 8 ml 30% H₂O₂ was added gradually. Then the resulting mixture was heated at about 50 °C with constant stirring for 8 h. It was then diluted, acidified and filtered. Finally column chromatography of crude solid gave the pure product (**6**), m.p. 180–182 °C.

General method for DAIB oxidation of flavonol :

Flavonol (1.5 ml) was dissolved in an alcohol (10 ml). Then DAIB (1.5 mmol) was added to it in three portions. Resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h. Then the solvent was removed in vacuum. Finally column chromatography of the crude material furnished the pure product.

[N.B. : Same procedure was applied for DAIB oxidation of 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromone (**6**) to obtain product **10**]

2,3-Dimethoxy-3-hydroxyflavanone (**2**) : m.p. 144–145 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-petrol, yield : 78%) (Found : C, 66.82; H, 4.90. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄O₅ : C, 67.12; H, 4.92%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3445 (free O-H), 3042, 2980, 2895, 1700 (C=O), 1605, 1575, 1450, 1378, 1295, 1230, 1140, 1065, 985, 875, 750 and 710 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.45 (6H, s, OCH₃), 2.52 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D₂O, free O-H), 7.02–7.21 (2H, m, H-6 and H-8), 7.42–7.48 (3H, m, H-3', H-4' and H-5'), 7.60 (1H, dt, *J* 8 and 2 Hz, H-7), 7.75–7.84 (2H, m, H-2' and H-6') and 7.94 (1H, dd, *J* 8 and 1.9 Hz, H-5).

3,3-Dihydroxy-2-ethoxyflavanone (**4a**) : m.p. 130–132 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-petrol, yield : 65%) (Found : C, 67.92; H, 5.38. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆O₅ : C, 68.05; H, 5.38%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3480 (free O-H), 3430 (chelated O-H), 3042, 2960, 2895, 1685 (C=O), 1600, 1570, 1455, 1380, 1290, 1230, 1145, 1070, 995, 870, 750 and 730 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.98 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, CH₃), 2.5 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D₂O, free O-H), 3.28–3.46 (2H, m, -OCH₂-), 4.85 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D₂O, chelated O-H), 7.10–7.19 (2H, m, H-6 and H-8), 7.44–7.49 (3H, m, H-3', H-4' and H-5'), 7.61 (1H, dt, *J* 8 and 2 Hz, H-7), 7.78–7.84 (2H, m, H-2' and H-6') and 7.96 (1H, dd, *J* 8 and 1.8 Hz, H-5).

3,3-Dihydroxy-2-isopropoxyflavanone (**4b**) : m.p. 120–121 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-

petrol, yield : 57%) (Found : C, 68.66; H, 5.66. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$: C, 68.76; H, 5.78%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3515 (free O-H), 3500 (chelated O-H), 3045, 3020, 2975, 2920, 1695 (C=O), 1600, 1575, 1458, 1375, 1320, 1230, 1060, 980, 880, 740 and 690 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.773 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CH_3), 1.02 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CH_3), 2.5 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , free O-H), 3.85–3.94 (1H, septet, J 6.2 Hz, $-OCH<$), 4.92 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated O-H), 7.08–7.16 (2H, m, H-6 and H-8), 7.45–7.49 (3H, t, J 9.6 and 5.9 Hz, H-3', H-4' and H-5'), 7.61 (1H, dt, J 8.2 and 2.4 Hz, H-7), 7.67–7.95 (3H, m, H-2', 6' and H-5).

Compound 5 : m.p. 172–173 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-petrol, yield : 70%) (Found : C, 72.12; H, 4.98. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$: C, 72.32; H, 5.00%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3420 (O-H), 3055, 2980, 2925, 2780, 1690 (C=O), 1600, 1572, 1455, 1360, 1318, 1258, 1218, 1182, 1142, 1080, 1055, 975, 940, 740 and 680 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.69 (1H, dd, J 11.4 and 3.0 Hz), 3.95 (1H, dd, J 11.4 and 3.0 Hz), 4.58 (1H, dt, J 11.2 and 3.0 Hz) and 4.71 (1H, dt, J 12.6 and 3.3 Hz, $O-CH_2-CH_2-O-$), 4.58 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , O-H), 7.08 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, H-8), 7.16 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-6), 7.20–7.36 (3H, m, H-3, H-4' and H-5'), 7.46 (2H, dd, J 7.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.62 (1H, dt, J 7.5 and 1.8 Hz, H-7), 7.85 (1H, dd, J 7.8 and 1.8 Hz, H-9).

3,3-Dihydroxy-2-methoxy-2-styrylchromanones (10a) : m.p. 122–124 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-petrol, yield : 77%) (Found : C, 69.02; H, 5.08. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$: C, 69.21; H, 5.17%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3470 (free O-H), 3440 (chelated O-H), 3000, 1680 (C=O), 1600, 1450, 1280, 1230, 1140, 1080, 980, 950, 750 and 700 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 3.20 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , free O-H), 3.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.89 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated O-H), 6.36 (1H, d, J 16.2 Hz, $-CH=CH-Ph$), 7.14 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, H-6 and H-8), 7.21–7.42 (4H, m, H-3', H-4', H-6' and H- α), 7.55 (2H, d, J 6.9 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.72 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, H-7), 7.95 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz, H-5).

3,3-Dihydroxy-2-ethoxy-2-styrylchromanones (10b) : m.p. 108–109 °C (colourless needles, crystallized from chloroform-petrol, yield : 71%) (Found : C, 69.94; H,

5.48. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$: C, 69.91; H, 5.57%); IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3485 (free O-H), 3440 (chelated O-H), 3040, 3010, 2960, 1675 (C=O), 1600, 1450, 1280, 1225, 1140, 1065, 970, 950, 760 and 701 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.93 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_3), 3.17 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , free O-H), 3.40–3.50 and 3.55–3.66 (each 1H, m, $-O-CH_2-$), 4.78 (1H, br.s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated O-H), 6.30 (2H, d, J 16.2 Hz, $-CH=CH-Ph$), 7.29–7.34 (3H, m, H-3', H-4' and H-5'), 7.45 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.54 (1H, t, J 7.8 Hz, H-7), 7.86 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, H-5).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have synthesized 3,3-dihydroxy-2-alkoxyflavanones and 3,3-dihydroxy-2-alkoxy-2-styrylchromanones by DAIB oxidation of flavonols and 3-hydroxy-2-styrylchromones respectively in different alcohols applying simple procedure at room temperature and in each case solvent addition product was formed in good yield.

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